

A STRUCTURED FRAMEWORK FOR INTERNATIONAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT COMMUNICATION RELATED RISKS IN A COVID-19 PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Purpose – Communication is a crucial mechanism for project coordination, monitoring and information gathering concerning possible deviations. Today's challenges, including cross-cultural teams, virtual teams, fast technology advancement and short time working have greater impact on project success. This paper aims to help corporations identify possible sources of risks related to global communication in a COVID-19 perspective by proposing a structured framework, using the practical experience and theoretical academic literature.

Methodology/approach – The search for communication risks is sought at the four communication dimensions: Global Communication planning, Global Stakeholder Management, Global Communication tools & Methodologies and Motivating and protecting people's health and safety. Assessing performance of project global team, considering the challenges of COVID-19 crisis. The relevant research papers and web literature are considered as a basis for conceptual framework creation. Filtering and structuring of information is advantaged by the experience of the author in project management, in a systematic framework. The results are filtered and evaluated by peers' insights from project management.

Findings – The paper attempts to develop a structured communication risk framework which can be used to identify the possible risk sources and improve the effectiveness of the communication in project management.

Research limitations/implications – In the current literature there are limited research publications proposing a structured framework for communication risks in a COVID-19 perspective.

Practical implications – The paper imposed theoretical contributions by identifying relevant literature, filtering the needed information and creating a structured framework of communication risks intended to provide support for future risk identification in concrete cases.

Originality/value – Changing in ways of collaboration and communication, ways of working and changing of communication tools require management attention and keeping the projects under control by identifying and managing risks. This approach imposed to bring significant value by helping organizations do that.

Key words: Communication risks, risk management framework, project stakeholders

Introduction

The COVID-19 crisis made the importance of a steady and reliable flow of information and the necessity of communication in global project management more visible. Several research papers show that an agile and transparent communication between stakeholders ensured the success of various projects which are on the verge of failure during the COVID-19 pandemic. Open and clear collaboration between stakeholders is key to reduce the influence of unplanned setbacks and keep projects ongoing in the most imperceptible way.

Considering this, there are numerous obstacles to overcome. Stakeholders need to be more flexible to ensure communication across different time zones, make up for the limited social interactions, set up

the necessary IT-Infrastructure, enable access to sufficient communication tools and adapt to a new work environment.

The most impactful adjustment is the adaptation towards a new work environment. A classic office is not necessarily needed anymore, COVID-19 enabled the office to be everywhere and anytime a day. A similar perception can be made regarding the daily working schedule meetings which have been set up all around the clock.

This paper proposes to identify the key challenges that companies in international businesses will need to face and define a structured framework for risks related to global communication. The framework is focusing on four main dimensions of communication Global Communication planning, Global Stakeholder Management, Global Communication tools & Methodologies and Motivating and protecting people's health and safety Assessing performance of project global team where can emerge potential risks. The framework aims to provide an overview about the risk sources with the potentially highest influence on global project management communication.

Background

Given the assumed contributions to this paper, describing the importance of communication in global project management and defining the main challenges faced by project management as a result of Covid 19 pandemic, constitutes the basis for framework creation.

Global project communication

Communication is the pillar to ensure effective and efficient global project management. Projects with a high level of complexity requires collecting, exchanging and distributing of a high amount of information. On this basis correct and relevant information must be provided to the right stakeholders in the right time and through the right methods and channels (Butt & Naaranoja, 2016).

The connection within project members is often limited by personal preferences and individual actions, instead of putting effort to create a multilayered project team. Such attitude and mindset lead to failures in projects and put the success in danger. To avoid this and increase the success rate of projects communication is the key, moment-to-moment communication of task assignments, responsibilities, milestones, issues and problems. Preventive corrective actions rely on the speed of communication among stakeholders. In Covid-19 times stakeholders have less opportunity for face-to-face communication and lose non-verbal aspects of communications (Iqbal, 2015). While the stakeholders are in remote office in an isolated office space the social competences decrease, as well the aspects of teamwork and coordination are negatively impacted. Stakeholders operate in the virtual environment and have to face serious communication issues, and miscommunication. This makes the generic process of building trust within a global team significantly more difficult.

But especially in a pandemic crisis as COVID-19 a clear and quick communication between stakeholders is the most important aspect for success.

The results of literature analysis related to challenges of Covid 19 on project management and their potential influences are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Challenges of COVID 19 on project management

Covid 19 pragmatic challenges in PM	Potential influence	Sources
New working environment	<p>Remote project communication and collaboration:</p> <p>Changing in ways of collaboration and communication between project associates</p> <p>Change of work relations between peers</p> <p>Change in communication tools: videoconference, audioconference, email, chat, phone, digital sharing of documents</p> <p>Remote working, including work from home:</p> <p>Different mindset and behaviours concerning working across cultures (team engagement, commitment and support)</p> <p>Changing in working time, move to short working time, absenteeism, reduction and restriction of overtime, limited human resources available (schedule delays for sample, trials, testing, certification, insufficient validation with impact on quality)</p> <p>Work flexibility: scheduling meetings at late times and expectation of availability</p>	(Deloitte, 2020) (Binder, 2009) (Robbins , 2020)
Stakeholders collaboration across globe	<p>Challenges in communication due to shutdown of plants with differences in ramp-up timing</p> <p>Lack of transparency with regard to Covid measures with customer and supplier and other partners</p> <p>Lack of transparency related project tasks progress of other team members</p> <p>Issues in sharing concrete informations concerning project context</p> <p>Single sourcing, without back-up supplier</p>	(pwc, 2020) (Sonta, 2020)
Remote Management	<p>Changes in leading of people: balance between employee productivity and wellbeing, identifying new modalities of connection with people (human emotions cannot be expressed digitally)</p> <p>Flat hierarchy: enable trust and independency to move the task and project forward</p>	(Deloitte, 2020) (J., 2007)

A framework related global communication risks

Although communication is the main driver in influencing the project management effectiveness, usually there is little concern about this. Even so, the practitioners cited several difficulties within communication process with direct impact on project success. (Pritchard, 2014) In this context project manager and related stakeholders need to address critical communication activities together with their risk to improve the communication effectiveness and avoid potential failure of the project. The author undertook a critical and extensive research of the present literature and web information, which created the basis of the following framework. Additional the creation of the framework was benefiting the experience and current position of the author in project management. Selection of relevant risk sources and validation of results were determined by consultation with several peers from project management and quality management field. The results of the analysis are described in Tab.2 into a structured framework related risk sources for global communication with considerations of current situation faced by Covid 19.

Table 2 A framework for communication related risks in international project management

Ref	Communication dimensions	Communication risk sources
<p>(Reed & Knight, 2010), (J., 2007)</p>	<p>1. Global Communication planning</p>	<p><i>Sources of risks related to communication planning:</i></p> <p>1.1 a Identifying needed resources: stakeholder availability and flexibility</p> <p>1.1 b Defining communication method, duration and frequency</p> <p>1.1 c Communication standards and template: meeting schedules (cannot be followed due to Kurzarbeit, plant shutdown)</p> <p>1.1 d Identifying the stakeholder limitations: Kurzarbeit, reduced office hours, plant shut down</p> <p>1.1e Updating periodically the communication plan: adapt the current plan to upcoming changes</p>
		<p><i>Communication crisis:</i></p> <p>1.2 a Defining of crisis team for emergency situations, including cross-functional and cross-cultural people, back-up for key personnel</p> <p>1.2 b Plan escalation modes and appropriate task force</p> <p>1.2 c Working infrastructure and tools for remote working: HW and SW tools</p> <p>1.2 d Plan emergencies response: considering ways of messaging (modes of tone, chosen words, communication style) & information flow, presence of leaders</p> <p>1.2 e Define appropriate working models that reach the needed performance and productivity and meet the health requirements (working at the office, remote, from home, etc.)</p>
<p>(Filev, 2012), (Nevogt, 2019), (Butt & Naaranoja, 2016), (Pullan & Prokopi, 2016), (Iqbal, 2015)</p>	<p>2. Global Stakeholder Management</p>	<p>2.1 Defining key stakeholders: public authorities, customer, key team members, preparedness of critical suppliers</p> <p>2.2 Stakeholder inclusion and connection:</p> <p>2.2 a Managing communication and maintain trust and confidence across stakeholders</p> <p>2.2 b Involving new team members within the team</p> <p>2.2 c Meeting schedule: managing teams across different cultures and different time zones</p> <p>2.2 d Managing cultural differences and language barriers to avoid misunderstandings</p> <p>2.2 e Ensure engagement & commitment of the right stakeholders, at the right time and through the right methods</p> <p>2.2 f Communication awareness: establish stakeholder awareness about communication channels where informations are updated</p> <p>2.2 g Establishing transparency in communication and actions: constant interaction to identify possible constraints</p> <p>2.3 Management and decision making: communication capacity of stakeholders, flexibility in decision making</p> <p>2.4 Analyze and understand require. and what the people feel about current situation: communication speed (early, fast, often), decision making transparency and speed, the exchange of information including project requirements, activities, drawings, samples, test results</p> <p>2.5 Provide relevant information sets to stakeholders</p>

<p>(Carney, 2015), (Zulch, 2014), (Rajkumar, 2010)</p>	<p>3. Global Communication tools, methodologies and techniques</p>	<p>3.1 Virtual collaborative methods: media & audio, video conference methods impact the trust between stakeholders</p> <p>3.2 Face to face interaction and relationship building: establish social interaction</p> <p>3.3 Written communication: ensure understanding of sent message and providing of appropriate response message</p> <p>3.4 Adopting compatible technologies</p> <hr/> <p>3.5 Collecting, distributing and exchange of informations using platforms and digital tools (sharepoints, cloud, communities, etc.): assure transparency of work packages and project information within the stakeholders</p> <p>3.6 Establish a clear versioning of documents, without risk of mixing the documentation, avoiding confusion and misunderstandings</p>
<p>(Filev, 2012), (Nickson & Siddons, 2004)</p>	<p>4. Motivating and protecting people's health and safety. Assessing performance of project global team</p>	<p>Project performance assessment</p> <p>4.1 Defining a motivation and communication strategy by sharing empathy, transparency and connection trough constant dialogue</p> <p>4.2 Establishing communication rules/ behaviours for reporting of project tasks results</p> <p>4.3 Assessing the capacity and prioritization of tasks</p> <p>4.4 Implementing a digital work performance tool for project team</p> <p>4.5 Monitoring and assessing constantly communication</p> <p>4.6 Adapting the project leading to the new working models</p> <p>4.7 Updating project documents and relevant procedures</p>

Discussion and conclusions

For companies aiming to achieve effective communication and successful project management, identifying and assessing of current risks and continuously adapting to the upcoming changes is a prerequisite. Covid 19 request a reinterpretation of working models, communication methods and strategies, infrastructure and nevertheless management of project team and stakeholders.

Dealing with new ways of communication, new working models and multiple parties with different communication strategies and availability limitations may affect to keep the project schedules tight and the output at requested and expected quality. To keep the project under control project managers need to adopt and implement a holistic approach for risk identification in Planning of communication, Stakeholder management, Communication tools, methodologies and techniques and assessing of motivation and performance of people. This paper attempts to support the project managers to identify the processes and activities with emphasize potential risks for communication.

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